

Studies of some mixed valence polyoxomolybdates

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The studies on the conditions of formation, preparation and analyses of four new mixed triheteropoly compounds have been carried out by pH measurements, thermometric titrations, chemical and atomic emission spectral methods. The compounds were finally characterized by UV-visible, IR, DTA, TGA, DTG and X-ray diffraction patterns.

Polyoxomolybdates with terminal oxygen atom are reducible in one or two electron steps to mixed valence polyanions^{1,2}, called heteropoly blues. It has been established that heteropoly anion, e.g., $[PV^VW_{11}O_{40}]^{4-}$ differs from the corresponding heteropoly blue, $[PV^{IV}W_{11}O_{40}]^{5-}$ only in the degree to which the valence electrons are trapped on a single metal atom. In literature^{3,4}, there are direct evidences for the presence of weakly trapped electrons in heteropoly blues and also for the intervalence charge transfer upon optical and ESR spectra. As a part of our investigation of polyoxomolybdates, the present communication deals with the preparations and characterization of potassium and guanidinium salts of four mixed triheteropoly molybdovanadoniobates and molybdovanadotantalates.

Results and discussion

The conditions of formation of potassium and guanidinium salts containing heteroatoms in four heteropolyoxomolybdates of general formula $[ZV_2Mo_{10}O_{40}].H_2O$ (where Z = Nb or Ta) have been carried out by pH measurements and thermometric titrations as discussed in our earlier communications. The approximate range of pH at which the compounds could be isolated was found to be 2.8 to 3.6. The metal contents of the compounds were determined by standard chemical methods and the results of such observations were corroborated by ICP atomic emission spectra. The aqueous solution of the compounds, $K_5[NbV_2Mo_{10}O_{40}].18H_2O$ and $K_5[TaV_2Mo_{10}O_{40}].24H_2O$ were examined spectrophotometrically in various buffer solutions to investigate their stability. A distinct characteristic absorption maxima at 340 nm ($\epsilon \approx 1.32 \times 10^3 M^{-1} cm^{-1}$) and minima at 322 nm ($\epsilon \approx 1.05 \times 10^3 M^{-1} cm^{-1}$) are observed for: $K_5[NbV_2Mo_{10}O_{40}].18H_2O$ in 0.01 M $K_2SO_4 - 0.02 M KHSO_4$ buffer solution (pH = 2.8). The absorption maxima remain almost unchanged when the spectrum of the compound was taken in 0.1 M $CH_3COOK - 0.1 M CH_3COOH$ (pH = 3.1). Thus from these observations it is

clear that the complex anion which is stable at pH 2.5 ($K_2SO_4 - KHSO_4$ buffer) obeyed Beer's law to 5% in the concentration range of 10^{-2} to $10^{-4} M$.

The compound shows sharp IR bands at 780–840 cm^{-1} (Mo-O-Mo bridging) and strong bands at 830–910 cm^{-1} due to independent Mo-O stretching vibrations. The bands of Mo-O and Mo-O-Mo are distinguishable although observed nearly at the same region⁶. The medium bands in the range of 920–980 cm^{-1} may be assigned to V-O stretching vibrations in octahedral co-ordination⁷ and those in the range of 480–452 cm^{-1} correspond to central Nb-O linkage. The peaks at 3420–3310 and 3180–3100 cm^{-1} region (asymmetric, symmetric O-H stretching) correspond to those of peripheral water molecules. The peaks at 1640–1600 cm^{-1} correspond to H-O-H bridging mode of water, whereas those in the lower frequency region 645–580 cm^{-1} are due to O-H liberation of lattice water. The N-H band⁸ in guanidinium salt was found at 1425–1380 cm^{-1} .

Preliminary X-ray data of the crystalline samples were recorded by rotation and Weissenberg photographs. The densities were determined by floatation method using carbon tetrachloride-bromoform mixture. The crystal data are as follows: $K_5[NbV_2Mo_{10}O_{40}].18H_2O$: orthorhombic; $a = 1.4012 \times 10^1 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 1.21 \times 10^1 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 1.3625 \times 10^1 \text{ \AA}$; $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$; $V = 2.31005 \times 10^3 \text{ \AA}^3$; space group $D_{2h}^2 P_{nnn}$; $Z = 2$; $\rho_{calc} = 3.36 \text{ g dm}^{-3}$; $\rho_{obs} = 3.28 \text{ g dm}^{-3}$; $M_{obs} = 2.282 \times 10^3$, against $M_{calc} = 2.34287 \times 10^3$. $K_5[TaV_2Mo_{10}O_{40}].24H_2O$: hexagonal; $a = 1.1750 \times 10^1 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 1.1750 \times 10^1 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 1.4750 \times 10^1 \text{ \AA}$; $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$; $V = 2.11080 \times 10^3 \text{ \AA}^3$; $Z = 2$; $\rho_{calc} = 4.57 \text{ g dm}^{-3}$; $\rho_{obs} = 4.07 \text{ g dm}^{-3}$; $M_{obs} = 2.858 \times 10^3$ against $M_{calc} = 2.90703 \times 10^3$.

The X-ray powder diffraction pattern of the compound, $[C(NH_2)_3]_5[NbV_2Mo_{10}O_{40}].20H_2O$ recorded under $CuK\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.5412 \text{ \AA}$) with Ni filter, revealed the maximum relative intensity I/I to be 41 with respect to interplaner

Table 1. Analytical data of TGA curves

Compd.	273–373		373–473		473–573		573–703 K	
	% of weight loss	No. of water moecules lost	% of weight loss	No. of water moecules lost	% of weight loss	No. of water moecules lost	% of weight loss	No. of water moecules lost
$K_5[NbV_2Mo_{10}O_{40}] \cdot 18H_2O$	3.83	5	3.07	4	3.83	5	3.07	4
$[C(NH_2)_3]_5[NbV_2Mo_{10}O_{40}] \cdot 20H_2O$	4.40	6	3.66	5	2.93	4	3.66	5
$[K_5(TaV_2Mo_{10}O_{40})] \cdot 24H_2O$	5.37	8	3.39	5	4.93	7	2.97	4
$[C(NH_2)_3]_5(TaV_2Mo_{10}O_{40}) \cdot 18H_2O$	4.30	6	2.87	4	2.15	3	3.58	5

distance 14.7. The 100 point I/I correspond to 'd' values 9.9 Å. The density of the compound was found to be 4.216 g dm⁻³.

The thermogravimetric analysis⁹ was performed by taking 25 mg of the compound at constant heating rate of 10 K min⁻¹. Keoline was taken as reference material for these experiment which have been carried out in air using alumina crucible. From the analysis of TGA graph, the percentage loss in weight of the compounds at different range of temperature, showing the corresponding loss of no of water molecules have been recorded in Table 1. The characteristic endothermic peaks upto the range of 573 K correspond to the loss of water of crystallisation and peaks at 573–703 K indicated the loss of co-ordinated water. A plateau followed by a number of weak exothermic peaks above 650–750 K, are due to the decomposition of heteropoly anionic cage to lower oxides of the constituent metal atoms, which were confirmed by total insolubilities of the ignited samples at this temperature. The IR spectra of the ignited samples further confirmed the complete decomposition of the heteropoly oxometallic cage.

Experimental

Potassium hexaniobate, $K_7HNb_6O_{19} \cdot 13H_2O$ and potassium hexatantalate, $K_7HTa_6O_{19} \cdot 16H_2O$ were freshly prepared¹⁰. All other reagents used were of A.R. grade. The solutions were prepared in distilled water. The metals were estimated using an A.R.L. 3410 (Switzerland) atomic emission photometer and C, H and N by Coleman analyser. The IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer. The X-ray data were recorded on a D 500/501 (Siemens) instrument. DTA, DTG and TGA experiments were carried out on a STA 409 (West Germany) analyser.

Potassium 10-molybdo 2-vanadoniobate, $K_5[NbV_2Mo_{10}O_{40}] \cdot 18H_2O$:

Potassium metavanadate (0.6 g, 4.34 mmol) in aqueous solution (20 cm³) was added slowly to an aqueous solution

(60 cm³) of molybdic acid (3 g, 16.67 mmol), to which an aqueous solution (15 cm³) of potassium hexaniobate (0.3 g, 0.254 mmol) was added dropwise with constant stirring maintaining the pH of the solution at 3.2 using glacial acetic acid. Thereafter the whole of the reaction mixture was heated over a controlled temperature bath for 12 h in a round bottom flask provided with a series of potash bulb guard tubes which absorb CO₂ from air, thus hydrolysis of hexaniobates due to the presence of atmospheric CO₂, was easily avoided. The reaction mixture was left in vacuum for three days. The pale yellow powdery compound formed was filtered from the mother liquor, washed with ethanol and recrystallized from hot water to get small fine shining crystal of the compound (yield 2.3 g).

Guanidinium 10-molybdo 2-vanadoniobate $[C(NH_2)_3]_5[NbV_2Mo_{10}O_{40}] \cdot 20H_2O$:

It was prepared by metathesis from the potassium salt of the compound mentioned above. It can also be prepared by ion exchange process. A solution of potassium 10-molybdo 2-vanadoniobate (3 g, 1.280 mmol) in hot water (100 cm³) was treated with guanidinium hydrochloride (0.3 g, 3.126 mmol) in water (100 cm³). The mixture was digested on a water bath for 4 h and left over night, light orange needle shaped crystals were obtained which were procured after 3 days (yield 2.29 g).

Potassium 10-molybdo 2-vanadotantalate, $K_5[TaV_2Mo_{10}O_{40}] \cdot 24H_2O$:

An aqueous solution (20 cm³) containing potassium metavanadate (0.6 g, 4.34 mmol) was added slowly with constant stirring to aqueous solution (100 cm³) of molybdic acid (3 g, 16.67 mmol). The reaction mixture was warmed on a water bath to which an aqueous solution (20 cm³) of potassium hexatantalate (0.3 g, 0.153 mmol) was added slowly with vigorous stirring maintaining the pH at 3.5 with glacial acetic acid and then it was heated under controlled temperature bath at 80° for 8 h in a round bottom flask fitted with potash bulb guard tubes, as explained for preparation of the previous compound. The solution was evapo-

Table 2. Analytical data of the polyoxomolybdates

Compd	Found (Calcd.) %						
	K	Nb/Ta	V	Mo	C	N	H
$K_5[NbV_2Mo_{10}O_{40}].18H_2O$	8.56 (8.42)	4.07 (4.01)	4.46 (4.40)	4.04 (4.47)	–	–	1.57 (1.55)
$[C(NH_2)_3]_5[NbV_2Mo_{10}O_{40}].20H_2O$	–	3.65 (3.78)	4.01 (4.15)	38.85 (39.09)	2.35 (2.44)	8.44 (8.55)	2.85 (2.82)
$K_5[TaV_2Mo_{10}O_{40}].24H_2O$	9.57 (7.76)	6.33 (7.21)	3.56 (4.06)	38.56 (38.24)	–	–	2.05 (1.91)
$[C(NH_2)_3]_5[TaV_2Mo_{10}O_{40}].18H_2O$	–	6.75 (6.88)	3.60 (3.82)	36.20 (36.53)	3.50 (3.19)	11.50 (11.19)	2.25 (1.59)

rated to one third of its volume at low temperature and left for crystallisation under vacuum, the bright orange crystalline compound appeared after three days, were washed with ethanol and dried (yield 2.14 g).

Guanidinium 10-molybdo 2-vanadotantalate, $[C(NH_2)_3]_5[TaV_2Mo_{10}O_{40}].18H_2O$:

It was prepared as bright orange crystal by metathesis using stoichiometric amount of aqueous solution (100 cm³) of $K_5[TaV_2Mo_{10}O_{40}].24H_2O$ (3 g, 1.031 mmol) with aqueous solution (20 cm³) of guanidinium hydrochloride (0.3 g, 3.126 mmol). The compounds were analysed by standard methods as reported in our earlier communication and results so obtained were confirmed by using ICP atomic emission spectra. C, H and N were determined by elemental analysis whereas oxygen by difference. The molecular formula of the compounds were assigned on the basis of well established Keggin's anion. All the synthesised compounds gave satisfactory metal and elemental analyses.

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